

Are Imagination and Concentration a Priority in Projecting Solution?

Bulent Ozdemir

To cite this article *Bulent Özdemir, Science, Volume 5, No. 4, 2023, pp. 01 – 21. - 0099-0001-2304-0201.*

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Prof. Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

CURRENT SCIENCE

journal with a multi-science peer-review. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

- *The magazine is published monthly.*

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this* ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

It's possible that the title of this article prompted a strange query in your mind. It is not impossible for the answer or solutions to become readily apparent. Everyone agrees that one of the most important qualities an educated person can possess is creativity. Imagination is a trait that should be shown by anybody who has received an education. Despite this, it is important to try to explain, in as much detail as possible, why educators should take imagination seriously and why imagination is essential to the area of education. To begin, providing an explanation of the factors that contribute to such behavior might assist us in developing strategies and environments that are more likely to pique the interest of children's imaginations. Second, expressing them may disclose potentially unanticipated educational repercussions because we comprehend the principle of imagination. Finally, it is abundantly obvious that the conception of imagination that we have is both comprehensive and intricate at the same time. It is also painfully evident that different people

CURRENT SCIENCE

often mean quite different things when they use the phrase in their conversations. Considering this, providing an explanation of the factors that led to its considerable consideration in educational contexts may be beneficial in elucidating the different implications it carries. Fourth, general and rather hazy support for the growth of imagination in education is most commonly limited to dealing with a rather lackluster sense of novelty in art self-expression and other areas of the curriculum. Elaborating on the reasons why the development of imagination is important for education can help clarify its role in the curriculum. And lastly, the fifth thing to take into consideration is that the standard structures and methods of modern education, which have been summed up in several publications, are constructed on concepts that do not expressly acknowledge imagination as an essential component of education. One further way of thinking about why creativity is so important to the teaching and learning process is to investigate the preconceptions that now serve as the foundation for educational practice.

Keywords: *Dreaming, Concentration, Projecting, Education and Concentration*

Introduction

When it comes to teaching, everyone knows that you should "start where the kids are." It would be irresponsible not to acknowledge the significance of the findings that led to the development of this idiom and many others like it. But, once we grasp its significance as a practice guide and begin to think carefully about it, the apparently straightforward guidance that it gives begins to seem to be quite overpowering. Where do the students typically sit in a conventional classroom? The concept that is conveyed by the cliché is often used to support the selection of curricular content that is a component of the familiar environment to which pupils belong. This justification may take the form of a beginning point for units or lessons. It is also used to justify an effort to classify students' stages of development, skill levels, relevant previous knowledge, and distinct learning styles. This is only one of the many uses of this concept. They have the potential to be of wonderful use in assisting with the planning of an effective classroom instruction. Yet, the most common uses of the notion in connection to the topic of the curriculum and psychological states are both susceptible to interpretations that are educationally ineffective. It is widespread practice to simplify the complexities of epistemological and psychological theories by reducing them to assertions

CURRENT SCIENCE

about "where pupils are." These assertions, however, seem to disregard the reality that pupils have creative faculties.

Sadly, many instructors seem to have accepted certain student preconceptions without questioning their validity, which has the impact of preventing students from recognizing "where students are." When it comes to the subject matter of the curriculum, the patterns of interest with which pupils might begin to inspire themselves are, for the most part, confined to the known substance of their day-to-day experiences. When it comes to psychological states, the stereotype of students' thinking is often restricted to descriptions of students' logical and arithmetic cognitive skills. This is the case since logic and mathematics are cognitive talents that are related to academic success. We can take a deeper look at these limiting prejudices and give a more nuanced view on the situation when we incorporate the creative lives of children in our "Where are the kids?" evaluation.

The concept that the most interesting content can be found in their local environment and from the experiences they have daily appears to be completely illogical, and the concept that their logical and mathematical abilities determine what they are capable of accomplishing appears to be insufficient. This pertains to the pupils' cognitive capacities, developmental stages, various learning methods, and so on. This is not to argue that attempting to study or understand what parts of students' local settings and day-to-day experiences may play a role does not have any merit. It is crucial that things that were once major discoveries may become stereotypes that begin to undermine the function they were originally meant to serve. This can happen rather easily. We feel that the degeneration that can be seen in these instances is a direct consequence of educational approaches that pay little or no attention to elements of the creative life of pupils. This article's goals are to (1) reassert the significance of paying attention to the imaginations of students and (2) investigate how the simple act of taking imagination seriously may influence some of the most widely held beliefs on the purpose of education. During the decades of attempts to make educational science more scientific by utilizing philosophical approaches and more rationally by utilizing psychological methods, the primary function of imagination has been overlooked for an inexplicable reason. This has occurred during the decades of these attempts.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Important are both John Dewey's remark that "imagination is a tool for assessment in every subject" (1966, p. 236) and John Warnock's assertion that "the cultivation of imagination should be the major purpose of education" (1976, p. 236) Both individuals made these observations in the same year. It is a representation of beliefs that have been fundamental to our society ever since the Romantic period (and much older, when we consider how the notion of "imagination" gained characteristics that were previously a part of the concept of "soul"), yet they are in rivalry with each other. In this context, we are not going to investigate why it is that the significance of imagination has been downplayed in educational discourse in favor of the benefits that educational philosophy and educational psychology have to offer. When we put creativity back at the center of our conversation, we must be prepared for the possibility that some of the standard topics discussed in today's educational discourse may be displaced from time to time. This is something we must be prepared for as we put creativity back at the center of our conversation. When beginning to author an essay on the topic, it is important to note that one cannot presuppose that all readers and listeners will have the same comprehension of what the term "imagination" means. But we all use the word with a level of reasonable confidence, which means that we are certain that other people will comprehend what we mean, and that other people will interpret what we mean in the same way that they interpret what they mean when they use this expression.

Hence, when we refer to "imagination," we are referring to a variety of talents that are shared by all of us. Intuitively, I think that the vast majority of individuals are able to reach a consensus on what elements fit inside this range. On the other hand, as soon as we attempt to expose it, categorize it, and define the components of it, it seems to produce conflicts, or at the very least displeasure with the characterizations.

Method

The challenge stems from the fact that our capacity for imagination resides at the core of many aspects of our life that are only partially understood, while imagination itself is both intricate and multidimensional. Every one of us has the power to form mental images of things that are not here or even do not exist, and we can also let these mental images to have the same type of influence on us as if they were actual and here in the room with us. It is quite challenging for us to adequately define the nature of these paintings since they are unlike any other picture that we are used to

CURRENT SCIENCE

seeing in the "outside" world. Nonetheless, it seems that various people may have quite diverse experiences of these pictures. Although some people may have unrestricted access to vivid quasi-pictorial visions, others may have experiences that are too hazy to properly be described as "images." It's one of those topics where "everything is captured, including even exactly what the problem is," and the same person can meet a spectrum of what appears to be "pictures" of various kinds or degrees. This is one of those topics where "everything is captured, including even exactly what the problem is" (Block, 1981, p. 5). The imagination occupies a kind of pivotal position at the intersection and interaction of a number of other determined aspects of our existence, such as perception, memory, the process of idea formation, emotion, and metaphor. This position allows the imagination to influence all these other aspects in a meaningful way. Some of the pictures we view seem to be "echoes" of things we have seen in the past, even though we can modify, combine, and exert control over the images we come across in wholly novel ways. Our memories seem to be able to change our views and keep their "echo" in ways that do not always, or maybe very frequently at all, need semi-pictorial representations of those perceptions. This may be because our memories are able to preserve the "echo" of those perceptions (as, for example, in situations of sound and smell). The ability of a person's imagination to "see" various solutions to a problem has virtually always been linked to the uniqueness of their ideas.

When we imagine something, it gives us the impression that it is happening right now or is genuine. So, our "coding" of and "access" to pictures is connected to our feelings. When we imagine something, it gives us the impression that it is happening right now or is genuine. The logic of the imagination is more readily compatible with the logic of metaphor than it is with any system of reason that can be explained in more detail by us. Every one of these problems comes with its own unique set of challenges, if not outright enigmas. However, as many others have shown in the past, it is not required to address all of them before stating anything significant about the function of imagination in education. This has been demonstrated by several people.

Imagination and Traditional Ways of Thinking

If we look at the way education is conducted in general, it would be reasonable to infer that the major objective of education is to provide students with the opportunity to acquire information,

CURRENT SCIENCE

skills, and attitudes that are suited to the context in which they find themselves. On the other hand, if we examine the work of the educational theorists who have had the most impact over the course of history, we find that the principal subject of their research is not the same. When we use Plato, Rousseau, and Dewey as examples, it becomes all too clear that their knowledge and skills, in the sense that seem to run our schools almost entirely, are only a small part of what interested them. This is a problem because our educational system seems to be run almost entirely by people with these types of knowledge and skills. When we take into consideration the writings of these three philosophers, this becomes very evident. According to them, the capacity to think independently of the normative beliefs and viewpoints that most people take for granted as they grow up is the most significant component of having an education. This is because receiving an education allows one to acquire this skill. They stress repeatedly that education is something that teachers and students in our classes often give extraordinarily little attention to. Inculcating information is obviously not insignificant to them; rather, their concern is dominated by the far more essential question of how to help a pupil to become an independent thinker who can perceive what conventional conceptions are. This topic is much more important to them. To put it in a condescending manner, education is a process that reawakens individuals to a state of mind that enables them to foresee situations different from those that exist now or have happened in the past. This state of mind is necessary for people to be able to imagine new possibilities. The educational programs that are provided are reflective of the many pedagogical philosophies that exist on how young children might be helped to develop into educated people and which pedagogical philosophies are used. Plato advocated for a curriculum that was very regimented and lasted for fifty years so that the minds of his greatest pupils may be liberated from the confines of doxa, which is another name for conventional thinking. Rousseau proposed that his pupil's every thought should be influenced, and that the student should be stopped from learning to read until he was around twelve years old. This was done to ensure that his learner would not be swayed by the myriad of views that may be gleaned through everyday social dialogue as well as literature.

Throughout the learning process, Dewey proposed educational practices that would assist pupils to take on a more scientific, inquisitive, and skeptical perspective. Everyone agrees that one of the primary goals of schools is to socialize children, which means teaching them to comprehend,

CURRENT SCIENCE

acknowledge, and cherish the customary concepts and beliefs of the community of which they are a part. Students are introduced to these concepts and worldviews in the context of the classroom, which enables this goal to be achieved. If there is nothing to back up one's assertions, then one's imagination is nothing more than unfounded conjecture, and using it serves neither the person nor society. This perspective is shared by many individuals:

"We want the child to learn and engage to some extent with our common views, our common way of life" (Hanson, 1988, p. 137).

It is thought that having a mental life that is comprised of the customary ideas and attitudes of one's time and location constitutes a type of slumber or slavery. The terms "awakening," "liberating," and "release" are often used to describe education that goes beyond the norms of conventional indoctrination. (This is most people that are victims of either slavery or sleep, and they are not conscious of their plight.) It talks about releasing those who are held prisoner. "To be able to dream is to be free of conventional appearances" (Sutton-Smith, 1988, p. 10/11) is a quotation that is commonly repeated in education as a manner of addressing the educational entailment of experience. This quote was first published in Sutton-book Smith's in 1988. Its primary focus is in this area. That is to say, the process of education that enables us to not be governed by old perspectives, ideas, beliefs, and practices is what gives us our sense of empowerment.

It should be 'free', not 'free' or 'always free from all conventions'.

Some people consider mental existences that are comprised of the customary ideas and attitudes of one's time and location to be a type of mental slavery or slumber. "Awakening," "Liberating," and "Releasing" are common metaphors used to describe education that goes beyond conventional forms of socialization. (This accounts for most people who are victims of either slavery or sleep, and they are not aware of their status.) It talks about setting the prisoners free. It is a widespread practice in the field of education to use the citation "To be able to dream is to be free of

CURRENT SCIENCE

conventional appearances" (Sutton-Smith, 1988, p. 10/11) as a means of discussing the role that experience plays in education. Its primary concern is as follows. To put it another way, education is the process that gives us power or enables us to not be governed by old ways of thinking, ideas, beliefs, and behaviors.

Literature review

The portion of the task that requires interaction with students or the presentation of established standards is the one that requires the biggest amount of time. The difficulty of accomplishing even this duty to a satisfactory level is not intended to be downplayed by this revelation, which is another one of its purposes. Difficult; we do not have clear curriculum guidelines to achieve this; It clashes with what already consumes a lot of energy and, of course, exerts subtle but powerful pressures against the order and various kinds of regulation that are the bureaucratic needs of the school. It clashes with what already consumes a lot of energy and, of course, it clashes with what already consumes a lot of energy. As a direct consequence of this, the capacity to be liberated from these traditions is far less often acquired. It is just as necessary for this to be a dissertation on philosophy or sociology and to emphasize the idea that most outstanding educational thinkers see traditional thinking as the primary adversary of traditional thought. Instead of ignorance being the major opponent of education, education itself is the primary enemy. Conventional brains may be capable of a wide variety of things, including having an astronomically high IQ, doing well on academic performance tests, and possessing encyclopedic knowledge.

AN Whitehead referred to persons like these as the dullest people on the face of the earth. What they seem to be lacking is originality, which points to a severe lack of knowledge.

Imagination and traditional ways of thinking are not incompatible modes of thought. It does not run counter to logical thinking, but rather has the ability to fill rational thought with vigor, energy, and deeper significance. To put Bowra's thoughts on this topic into my own words, "By the use of his imagination, [person] is responsible for the existence of life and adds to the whole experience of life. [Person] does not want to play the role of a spectator but rather one of an active participant " (1949, p. .292). Hence, placing an emphasis on imagination helps to bring to our notice the fact that the most creative modes of thinking are also ones that have been the focus of the most

CURRENT SCIENCE

prominent educational thinkers throughout the course of history. They worked hard to find ways to ensure that this process was accompanied by a process that made these traditions intellectual servants rather than masters, but educational programs were not designed to prevent students from socializing and maturing in accordance with the traditions of the time and place in which they were raised. Therefore, it is not suggested that kids participate in these programs since they inhibit students' ability to socialize and mature in accordance with the norms of their time and location.

Whatever information you enter these storage and retrieval systems, whether they are based on wax tablets or parchment, books or computers, you will receive out of them precisely the same thing. One of the characteristics that sets them apart from many other kinds of systems is the presence of this attribute. The processes of storing knowledge and retrieving it are substantially dissimilar to those involved in the learning process of humans. Nonetheless, the way we think about ourselves is, sadly, influenced by our technology. Naturally, if you think about learning a fact like 100 degrees Celsius, which is the boiling point of water at sea level, and then repeating that fact, what you are doing is the reality is very similar to what occurs in real life. This is because the reality is remarkably like what happens when you are learning the fact. It is written down someplace using symbols, and it may be accessed later. It just so happens that the storage device in this situation is your brain, and the mechanism of accessing the information is your memory. This is a happy coincidence. If we allow our technology to define how we think about our intellectual processes, then one result that I believe is prevalent and highly destructive to education is the notion that learning is a process like enlisting information in one's memory for later retrieval. Because of this style of thinking, many have come to believe that education is a process that is analogous to recording symbols to recollect them later. In fact, the human mind seems to be rather poor at keeping this sort of record and reliably maintaining it through time, which is the very first item that we will highlight here.

A data written down on paper or recorded on a disk in a computer is far more trustworthy. Learning may be evaluated in this technologically analogous manner by determining the degree to which recordings are preserved and saved for eventual use in the subsequent examination. Exams of this kind are administered on a regular basis in schools, and the results are construed in a very direct manner as evidence of pupils' capacities for academic growth. Since this method has been around

CURRENT SCIENCE

for such a long time and is so prevalent in educational institutions, the definition of learning that is most frequently accepted involves some type of mechanical storing and retrieval. And how precisely does it violate any norms or standards? First things first, let's have a look at a few different items. The most significant issue with this strategy is that it pays no attention at all to the characteristics that give human learning its distinctive character. Humans tend to forget that the process by which the human mind "learns" is extremely different from the process by which a computer "learns," and that the way our memories are quite different from the way in which computers "remember" things. As we acquire new knowledge, the human mind does not just save the information for later use. It is plausible that it can do this, and if it is, we can use them to remember things like phone numbers or grocery lists even when we do not have a piece of paper available to write on. Even the most fundamental facts, like the fact that spiders have eight legs or that Vasco da Gama set sail from Lisbon in 1497 to travel across Africa and arrive in India the following year, are typically forgotten as soon as they are learned by most people. This is because most of the time, we simply do not store the information. In human brains, this input is processed as separate units after being received. For instance, we discovered that Vasco da Gama embarked on a journey of Africa in the year 1497 and landed in India the year after that. As we gain knowledge of anything, that knowledge becomes entwined with the ever-changing web of feelings, memories, intentions, and other mental states that comprise our existence.

The way in which we feel about insects in general and spiders will influence the way in which we see the facts that we know about spiders, as well as the way in which those facts will be colored emotionally. The adventures of Vasco da Gama are likely to elicit ideas of ships traveling along distant shorelines, as well as a spirit of exploration associated with those ships.

Findings

The intricate web of meaning structures that we already possess, which in turn is impacted by elements such as our emotions, ambitions, and so on, has a direct effect on whether we can recall specific knowledge and how successfully we are able to do so. The human memory is not a tidy, clean environment that can be organized into compartments or shelves, where knowledge may be kept until it is required. It is more analogous to a constant upheaval that is brought on by the feelings and objectives that are a part of us. Almost nothing is retrieved from human memory

CURRENT SCIENCE

exactly as it was first learnt. This is since the human memory is not fixed. There is a never-ending process of mixing and combining, and connections are continually being established, destroyed, and re-created. Every new piece of information is surrounded by an infinite number of connections, and there is also a never-ending process of mixing and combining. Making use of one's creativity is also a significant part of this endeavor, so keep that in mind. It is becoming increasingly obvious that human learning entails not just reflecting on what is going on in the world outside of one's brain, but also critically constructing or composing something new, and the connection between the two is becoming increasingly apparent (Bruner, 1986). Every person's thought process is unique, and they each add a distinct point of view and experience to the discussion of the world. The learner is challenged throughout the whole of the instructional process to assimilate all that is to be learnt into the network of separate meaning structures that has already been built in his mind. As a result, it is essential to restructure, as well as to reconsider the composition and the meanings. According to Warnock (1976), one of the most essential purposes of the imagination is to provide meaning to what one sees or hears. This is one of the most important roles of the imagination. If we consider the power of imagination and then investigate learning in the context of our growing capacity for imagination, we can zero in on the aspects of education that place an emphasis on the construction of meaning. That means giving the imagination the weight it deserves and considering how best to acquire knowledge in the context of our ever-growing comprehension of imagination. It is not the facts themselves, our talents, or anything we learn that generate meaning; rather, it is the link that is made between what is learnt and our thinking. But our brains are more than simply repositories of information; rather, they are dynamic hubs of activity in which emotions, objectives, and memories are intertwined with recently acquired information to give it meaning. Because of this, the random perspective of learning may seem to be so hopelessly complicated that the straightforward notion that is now widespread in school may seem preferable, despite the price of schooling.

If we are unable to explain why a spider has eight legs without resorting to emotion, purpose, meaning structures (whatever they are), or imagination, then it is feasible for us to quit up and acknowledge that we have been unsuccessful. I don't think it's as big of an issue as some people make it out to be we don't need to mix all of these various sets of complicated mental notions

CURRENT SCIENCE

simply to speak about learning. I don't think that's necessary. On the other hand, all that is asked of us is to bear in mind that the method in which humans learn is in no way analogous to the way in which knowledge is stored, and this is not an exceedingly difficult point to keep in mind. Accepting the findings seriously, in my opinion, is the most difficult step. And this is the moment at which real contemplation on one's imagination starts to demolish some of the well-known and deeply embedded components of the contemporary educational landscape. [C]ontemporary educational landscapes have been built on a foundation of rote memorization and rote learning.

When education is viewed as the process of accumulating knowledge and skills that are not related to emotions, intentions, human meanings, and imagination, the teaching methods, examinations, and curriculum that are utilized are likely to fall short of doing more than simply producing conventional thinkers.

Memory and Imagination

Memory and imagination have always had a close association in Western society, and this connection goes back an exceptionally long time. The foundations of this link may be found in the writings of Aristotle. This connection is not merely an intriguing truth about the past; rather, it is one that has a great deal of bearing for education in the contemporary world. A mentality has developed because of the language of progressivism, which was discussed earlier, that "rote learning," that is, learning in the traditional sense, is meaningless in terms of education and ought to be avoided. This mentality has led to the development of a mentality that "rote learning" is learning in the traditional sense. Underestimating the importance of memorizing and treating pupils as storage instruments for knowledge that is of little use to them is a waste of time, which is the key realization that occurs because of this realization being a naïve assumption most of the time. One of the clear implications that can be drawn from the consistent observation of the relationship between memory and imagination is that it is essential to memorize knowledge, facts, pieces of prose and poetry, formulas, and other such things to stimulate and develop one's imagination. This is one of the clear implications that can be drawn from the consistent observation of the relationship between memory and imagination. This is one of the many obvious repercussions that can be drawn from the connection between memory and imagination. The imagination is simply devoured by ignorance. And we are not aware of all the knowledge that we

CURRENT SCIENCE

know how to get but are unable to obtain, as well as all the information that we have learnt to acquire but are unable to acquire. Only when we have access to the knowledge that is stored in our memories can our imaginations be use. This idea may strike you as being completely counter to what was discussed in the section before this one. Although it may appear that I am arguing that students' imaginations are stifled if they are asked to acquire an excessive amount of knowledge and skills in a particular area, what we are stating is that students' imaginations ought to be appropriately stimulated by appropriately memorization large numbers of items.

Knowledge and Skills

When we take into consideration the point that was expressed previously regarding the necessity of information and talents that need to be remembered, we find that the two concepts are compatible with one another and make sense when taken together. For one's information and abilities to have any real-world application, the learning process must include the use of one's imagination. The appropriate treatment of how educators may facilitate the development of such creative thinking abilities in pupils requires a great deal more room than is allotted to it in an article (see Egan, 1988, 1990). Having said that, the point that must be addressed here is that the development of children's imaginations cannot progress without first absorbing and then remembering a vast number of knowledge spanning a broad range of themes. This is an essential step in the process. From the late 1980s, this concept has been regularly articulated in pedagogical writings that are characterized by their adherence to a so-called "neoconservative" worldview (e.g., Bloom, 1987; Hirsch, 1987; Ravitch & Finn, 1987). These neo-conservative works place a strong emphasis on the fundamental idea that education and knowledge are inexorably related, and that to have an education implies, to put it simply, to have a substantial amount of information. It is important to place emphasis on this aspect. On the other hand, as I have emphasized several times in the past, this connotation does not merely signify it. Since education is also deeply concerned with the meaning that a person develops for themselves as a person, imagination is of the utmost importance in this setting. Even if someone strictly adheres to the neoconservative pedagogical approach, they can still be one of the least interested persons throughout the whole of human history. What these publications are missing, however, is a clear understanding and attention to how information becomes meaningful in the lives of learners; how can we engage kids in creative

CURRENT SCIENCE

learning, in the way that I have coined the word here? When we state that certain books are missing, what exactly do we mean by that? Oral civilizations only pass on information that can be recalled from generation to generation. As a direct consequence of this, a substantial amount of social value was ascribed to methods that promoted recollection. Several of the solutions that were developed or envisioned included the use of rhyme, rhythm, and meter. In other words, it has been discovered that information that is structured in a rhythmic and rhyming sequence is simpler to recall than information that is not arranged in this way. This is because rhythm and rhyme help the brain to organize and store information.

It was also discovered that information, which is often referred to as the individual's tribal wisdom, was far simpler to recall if it was embedded with live images. This was one of the findings that was uncovered. Encodings of this kind sometimes take the shape of vivid imagery in the myths and legends of many cultures from throughout the globe. So, it seems logical to assume that the desire to retain knowledge is what first drives and develops many of the talents that we now term imagination. This is because the information must be remembered. The modeling of sound, the production of live images, and the structuring of narrative were the most significant early developments in social innovation. It was the technical linguistic tools and their effects on the mind that helped groups of people to be in harmony and remain relatively stable over unknown generations (Havelock, 1963, 1986; Lévi-Bruhl, 1985; Lévi-Strauss, 1966; Ong, 1982) [Havelock, 1963, 1986; Lévi-Bruhl, 1985; Lévi-Strauss, 1966; Ong, 1982]. As was said in another place, these discoveries do not have any bearing on the oral cultures that existed an exceptionally long time ago (Egan, 1988).

Argument

Their effect on the human mind was the source of their social importance. While our age is not as reliant on these practices as were earlier generations, they continue to play vital roles in the development of our psychology. They can direct us through the process of imaginative learning and the creative process of memorizing, which is the job that we need to accomplish. That is, learning may make use of them to aid memory in its process of establishing meaning, order, and meaning among the many contents of memory. According to the words of Brian Sutton-Smith (1988, page 22), the concept that "the mind is... a narrative issue" is garnering an increasing amount

CURRENT SCIENCE

of acceptance among individuals from all over the globe. It casts doubt on the long-held idea that there is a logical concern that works with abstract concepts when the mind functions properly and correctly as it should.

As a direct consequence of this, limited logical operations were the only ones for which a plausible explanation could be offered. It is becoming more common knowledge that these activities have their beginnings and origins in foundations that are metaphorical and narrative in nature (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Someone whose sense of logic was confined to what could be proven in a fashion that was comparable to formal logical style was the kind of person who could talk of a parent's "irrational" love for a kid. Once the "mind" is released from its confinement and connects with the imagination, the love that a parent feels for their kid is shown to be entirely logical. When it becomes increasingly apparent that the mind operates as a whole and that this integrity encompasses our bodies, the concept of the mind as a sophisticated calculator and the mind as computations of the mind becomes less and less tenable. It is now abundantly evident that rationality is not a set of skills that can be learned, but rather that it is connected to all of these previously disregarded attics, basements, and hidden chambers of the mind. These are the kinds of places where analogies, feelings, and the imagination are allowed to run rampant. Therefore, it has been rediscovered that we make sense of the world and our experiences through narratives, that we can remember items in narrative structures better than items that are organized logically in lists, and that we encode the information in our memory more deeply with emotional rather than logical associations. These discoveries were made possible by the fact that narratives have been around for a long time. Little children can manage metaphor with more ease and flexibility than older, educated children, etc., therefore these kinds of considerations are essential. Since the imagination is more apparent in the fabrication of fairy tales and in recognizing their coherence, the rediscovery of the narrative mind compels us to pay greater attention to the imagination. This is since our imagination plays a larger role in how we understand the cohesiveness of tales. Because of this, it has traditionally been believed to entail the development of more significant intellectual abilities, and this is something that learners of fairy tales need to undertake to become competent.

It was previously remarked by Northrop Frye, and I quote him on this: "The ability of listening to fairy tales is a fundamental training for the imagination" (1963, p. 49). The mind's capacity to

CURRENT SCIENCE

follow fairy tales, in addition to its ability to make sense of the world and find meaning in it, may be stimulated and increased, respectively, via the mind's ability to do both of these things.

Hearing many different stories can help complicate our understanding of and ability to use metaphor because metaphor is the connecting logic of storytelling, and because metaphor is a crucial component in the causation that connects stories, hearing many different stories can help complicate our ability to use metaphor. In a tale, the sequence of events that builds up to the climax is comprised of both logical and emotional components that interact with one another.

That is to say, the progression of events in fairy tales that is both understandable and logical does not rely simply on logic, even if they must be reasonable in some way; rather, it needs an emotional beat to function properly. The moment in which the fairy godmother makes her entrance takes place just after Cinderella bids farewell to her sisters before heading off to the ball. Yet, emotional causality assures that the connection between the two pictures is both instantaneous and immediate. If we were to follow a causal chain that was solely rational, we could need to witness activities such as dishwashing, dusting, throwing coal, or any other action. The process of being familiar with and acting out fairy tales may lead to the development of a variety of mental skills. Both *Ulysses* and *Finnegans Wake*, which were written by James Joyce, become understandable as we proceed through the book. Additionally, the intricate understanding of the narrative that is required to do this becomes more readily available to us, which enables us to make sense of not only our own experiences but also the world in which we live.

Discovering Ourselves

Because these capabilities, including our ability to derive meaning from experience, the development of narrative capacities of the mind, the ready use of metaphor, the integration of cognitive and emotional processes, the capacity to give meaning and meaning, and the inclusive imagination, are important educational goals. Our lives are "saw as reflecting a specific sort of narrative structure," according to this interpretation of what's going on, so to speak (MacIntyre, 1981, p. 163). Every single action or conduct, on its own, is meaningless; everything "makes sense when it finds its place in the tale" (MacIntyre, 1981, p. 196). The way that Barbara Hardy so eloquently expresses it is, "When we tell stories, we dream. As we tell stories, we dream. As we

CURRENT SCIENCE

tell stories, we recall. In storytelling, we must speculate. Throughout the tale, we are optimistic. In storytelling, we experience hopelessness. We put our faith in narratives. In story, we have reason to disbelieve. While telling a story, we plot. As we tell stories, we critique. In storytelling, we construct. We learn via the use of narratives. We despise lies in the tale " (1968, p. 5).

Because of this, it is necessary that students be given the opportunity to develop and be encouraged to do so if we want them to have an easy time comprehending the world around them, and if we want to place an emphasis on the components of the list that Barbara Hardy has provided us with above. And this style, which arises as fairy tales to help us remember things, is one area where the use of one's imagination is vitally necessary. Since it is not seen as being as productive as developing abilities in logic and mathematics, the development of the narrative style of the mind is generally regarded to be less of a priority in educational settings such as schools. Because enhancing one's ability to reason logically and calculate well is generally seen to be more productive. The dissemination of practical information, which is the primary objective of educational institutions, is something that students can grasp very quickly and readily.

Young people need to be made aware, as one of the roles of education, which leading a creative life may result in rewards, some of which may not be immediately useful but are nonetheless desired. And probably most crucially, for the purposes of education, access to narratives seems to be open to everybody, regardless of their level of reading, and they provide a direct route to the acquisition of any information. It is important for teachers to instill "respect for the narrative as everyone's basic skill but also as a universal gift to be shared with others," since doing so would be a sensible move (Coles, 1989, p. 30).

We would want to include social qualities like tolerance and justice to the list of educational principles that are a natural result of the growth of one's imagination. These sorts of social characteristics are examples of the kinds of social qualities that we would like to include in the list. It would be an exaggeration to imply that all the evil in the world is due to a mere lack of imagination, yet for certain people, this seems to be the case. A sizable portion of evil may be traced back to a lack of imagination on the part of its perpetrators, which stops them from

CURRENT SCIENCE

comprehending the fact that other people have distinct identities, that they can make their own choices, and that they have hopes and fears.

The development of this imaginative comprehension is an essential step in the process, but it does not ensure that we will eventually treat them in the same way we would like to be treated ourselves; all it does is ensure that we treat them in the way we would like to be treated. On the other hand, there are several additional connections that may be made between the ability to imagine and the action of being socially responsible. In the previous chapter, MacIntyre emphasized the point that the capacity to follow tales is tied to the ability to make sense of human experience. This is because our lives can only be understood in the framework of narratives, and MacIntyre's statement captures this point well. He sees that "man is basically a storytelling animal in his acts and practice as much as in his fictions," so drawing attention to the intricacy of our capacity to create fiction (1981, p. 201). Only within the framework of tales can our lives be comprehended in their entirety. There is no other way for us to comprehend any civilization, including our own, other than the collection of tales that serve as the society's original dramatic origins. Mythology, in the sense in which the term was originally used, is at the heart of everything.

And of course, this ethical canon, which spans from ancient fables to the heirlooms of the middle ages, lies at the heart of everything (1981, p. 201). Not only do stories pass on knowledge to their listeners, but they also "educate us in the virtues" Tales are valuable for both reasons. Stories are beneficial for 'educating us in the virtues' because they not only describe events and actions, but also arouse our emotions. This is because tales describe events and activities. It is exactly this power that leads some individuals, particularly those who are concerned in the education of young people, to have doubts about them and even dread them.

Conclusion

In this sense, tales are the instruments that we have at our disposal to demonstrate to others what it is like to feel the way that we do and to learn what it is like to feel the way that others do. Tales also provide us the opportunity to experience what it is like to put ourselves in the shoes of another person. Briefly, this story revolves on the concept of "the potential to exchange experiences" (Benjamin, 1969, p. 83). These kinds of tales ultimately become an integral part of who we are as

CURRENT SCIENCE

individuals (Coles, 1989, p. 128). By engaging in creative thought experiments, in which one imagines what it would be like to be someone other than oneself, one can begin to establish a prerequisite for treating others with respect in addition to treating oneself with respect. This is important because treating others with respect is a prerequisite for treating oneself with respect. At the very least, it is conceivable to view the biases that are so pervasive in our society as failures of creative progress. These prejudices may take the shape of bigotry based on religion, socioeconomic class, or racial intolerance. The capability of the narrative to engage one's imagination and, as a result, contribute to tolerance and a sense of justice must, of course, be measured against the story's ability to do the exact opposite of those things. If the story, for instance, is about Aryan supremacy and the liberation of the Nazis, then it has the potential to have an equal impact on the imagination and lead to consequences that are diametrically opposite to tolerance and social justice.

References

- Bruner, Jerome. (1986). Actual minds, possible worlds. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Canadian Public Health Association (CPHA). (2019). 5 Key Findings on Unstructured Play and Mental Health. Canadian Public Health Association. https://www.cpha.ca/sites/default/files/uploads/resources/play/play_5reasons_infographic_e.pdf
- Canadian Public Health Association (CPHA). (2019, Apr.). Resources and Services: Recess.
- Canadian Public Health Association (CPHA). (2019, Mar. 12). Children's Unstructured Play Position Statement. Canadian Public Health Association. <https://www.cpha.ca/childrens-unstructured-play>
- Canadian Public Health Association. <https://www.cpha.ca/recess>
- Colagrossi, M. (2018, Sept. 10). 10 reasons why Finland's education system is the best in the world. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/09/10-reasons-why-finlandseducation-system-is-the-best-in-the-world>

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Coles, Robert. (1989). *The call of stories: Teaching and the moral imagination*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Cullingford, Cedric. (1985). *Parents, teachers and schools*. London: Royce.
- Dewey, John. (1966). *Democracy and education*. New York: FreePress. (First published 1916).
- Egan, Kieran. (1986). *Teaching as storytelling*. London, Ontario: Althouse Press; Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1988; London: Routledge, 1988; Lisbon: Livros Horizonte, 1990.
- Egan, Kieran. (1988). *Primary understanding: Education in early childhood*. New York and London: Routledge.
- Egan, Kieran. (1990). *Romantic understanding: The development of rationality and imagination, ages 8-15*. New York and London: Routledge.
- Levi-Strauss, Claude. (1966). *The savage mind*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- MacIntyre, Alasdair. (1981). *After virtue*. Notre Dame, Indiana: University of Notre Dame Press.
- McFarland, Thomas. (1985). *Originality and imagination*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Mock, Ruth. (1971). *Education and the imagination*. London: Chatto and Windus.
- NewsWise. (2006, Oct. 4). *New AAP Report Stresses Play for Healthy Development*. Newswise. <https://www.newswise.com/articles/new-aap-report-stresses-play-for-healthy-development>
- Ong, Walter. (1982). *Orality and literacy*. London and New York: Methuen.
- Pinar, W. (Ed.). (1998). *The enthusiastic mind of Maxine Greene*. https://doi-org.qe2aproxy.mun.ca/10.4324/9780203980729_
- Polanyi, Michael. (1967). *The tacit dimension*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Ravitch, Diane, & Finn, Chester E., Jr. (1987). *What do our 17-year-olds know?* New York: Harper and Row.

Robinson, SK (2010). Bring on the learning revolution!

https://www.ted.com/talks/sir_ken_robinson_bring_on_the_learning_revolution/transcript#t-263212

Robinson, SK (2013, May 10). How to escape education's death valley

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wX78iKhInsc>

Rule, AC (2006). The components of authentic learning. *Journal of Authentic Learning*.

https://dspace.sunyconnect.suny.edu/bitstream/handle/1951/35263/editorial_rule.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Russ, SW, & Wallace, CE (2013). Pretend play and creative processes. *American Journal of Play*, 6(1), 136–148.

<https://www.journalofplay.org/sites/www.journalofplay.org/files/pdf-articles/6-1-articlepretend-play.pdf>

Sandseter, EBH, & Sando, OJ (2016). We don't allow children to climb trees. *American Journal of Play*, 8(2), 178–200.

<https://www.journalofplay.org/sites/>

www.journalofplay.org/files/pdf-articles/8-2-article-we-dont-allow-children-to-climb-trees.pdf

Sutton-Smith, Brian. (1988). In search of the imagination. "In K. Egan and D. Nadaner (eds.), *Imagination and education*." ("Imagination - Wikipedia") ("Imagination - Wikipedia") New York: Teachers College Press; Milton Keynes: Open University Press.

The Strong National Museum of Play. (2020). Play quotes. <https://www.museumofplay.org/education/education-and-play-resources/play-quotes>

Warnock, Mary. (1976). *Imagination*. London: Faber.